

1. Introduction

Significant changes that are currently taking place in the economic, political, cultural and other spheres affect all aspects of human life. And one of the most important issues in this process is the need for different approaches in the preparation of future specialists for professional activities. The main guidelines are not limited to the knowledge system, but are supplemented by a system of skills that allow one to integrate into professional activity. Therefore, the issues of studying and standardizing the process of socialization of students as a special socio-demographic group are especially important.

Studies on the problems of political socialization of student youth in the Russian Federation are contained in the works of A. V. Elekhin [1], A. S. Vatorlin [2], S. I. Sergeichik [3], E. V. Shichkova [4], I. A. Svertkov [5].

The relevance of studying the issues of socialization of student youth lies in the fact that this social group is the most educated part of the youth, and, therefore, it will become the base for recruiting the new ruling class of the Russian state, as well as the country's intellectual elite. Thus, the nature of the evolution of the political and administrative system of Russia of the future depends on the emerging model of socialization of student youth, including the political one.

In this case, the main task of a tourism excursion is to awaken among the guests an interest in the host country. Creating an exciting excursion that will not only fill the visitor with positive impressions, but also stimulate him/her to visit again is not an easy task. During an excursion for foreign tourists, this task is put not only before a guide, but also before an interpreter, who in this situation is faced with the problem of transferring a large amount of culture-specific information to other information.

The development of linguistic issues is of primary importance for identifying and explaining the specifics of the linguistic pictures of the world, which is reflected in the works of Yu. D. Apresyan [6], T. V. Bulygina, A. D. Shmelev [7], studies of the possibilities for building a model of a linguistic personality are presented in the works of V. I. Karasik [8], Yu. N. Karaulov [9], E. V. Krasilnikov [10].

The aim of the study was to examine multidimensional communication in the tourism sector. And to define an excursion as an effective way of understanding the world, receiving new information and acquiring new skills as one of the main components of organizing tourism products, which is an integral part of the Uralym project.

2. Methods

The socialization of youth is being implemented through a number of programs: volunteer work, participation in student teams, participation in a number of non-profit socially oriented

STUDENT'S SOCIALIZATION: PROBLEMS AND MECHANISMS OF IMPLEMENTATION THROUGH THE DEVELOPMENT OF A LINGUISTIC IDENTITY

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Abstract: This article announces the results of a study conducted within the framework of the Uralym project, revealing topical issues of youth socialization. The purpose of this article is to record the intermediate results of a comparative analysis and determine the areas of interaction and mutual influence of issues and problems of youth socialization. Particular attention is paid to promising opportunities for youth adaptation through the development and education of a linguistic personality. As part of the professional training of specialists, the parameters of the expansion and deepening of their linguistic worldview are investigated using the objects and methods of comparative sociolinguistics. The connection between new approaches to the formation of a linguistic personality and the socialization of youth through tourism, local history, history, culture, traditions of the region is revealed, and the possibilities and mechanisms of excursion rhetoric are used.

Keywords: socialization, linguistic personality, excursion rhetoric, domestic tourism.

projects, events, and others. The problem of activists in various youth organizations is the timing of their activity, which is limited to a year or two. Having received a one-time experience, immersion in various fields of activity, only 5 % decide to develop their career in this direction. Thus, the initiated social capital is only a small fraction of those, who could be involved in the processes of civil society renewal at different levels.

According to numerous studies and analysis of the statistical review of the document "Youth in Russia" [11], it was revealed that the greatest effect in terms of socialization is provided by the involvement in sports attractions, in second place is the participation in youth communities, in third place is volunteer activity, and the use of tourist opportunities and resources of culture and art is minimal. Our research proves a fact - tourist activities have the greatest multiplier effect.

The comparative analysis, displayed on Fig. 1, showed the

improvement in cognitive abilities, improved academic performance, multiple progress in terms of socialization among schoolchildren. A more vivid picture is presented by the analysis of academic performance, socialization and assimilation of student behavioral models using a similar approach.

To conduct the study, a method was proposed for calculating the effectiveness of an excursion, as a basic unit of tourist discourse in order to determine the connections and types of impact of elocution.

Fig. 1. Positioning elocution in excursion text reproduction

The links between these blocks are interdependent, since an insufficiently prepared linguistic personality cannot produce a high-quality basic text and use eloquent techniques in an individual text. The combination of basic concepts gives a highly positioned excursion with the highest possible effect: emotional, economic and extrapolation, so that the elocution effect can be represented as the sum of linguistic and extralinguistic techniques:

$$E = \Sigma(l + pf + nvt), \quad (1)$$

where E – elocution; l – the sum of linguistic techniques; pf – the sum of psycho-factors; nvt – the sum of non-verbal techniques [12].

Elocution can be represented as the sum of linguistic forms, psychophysical factors and non-verbal techniques, which can serve as a basic element in assessing the level of socialization of young people.

The concept of the language and speech culture of the communicator is very multifaceted. To use it correctly, you need to determine the main parameters and their functions. This requires a coordinate system – classification. The methodological approach to present information about the culture and traditions of the region acts as a marketing tool for promoting the image of Bashkortostan. The development of intercultural relations in the globalized conditions of interaction of modern society, linguocultural differences and changes in established ethno and sociocultural values are most clearly manifested in the tourism discourse.

3. Results

There are practically no behavioral models in society that would form the competencies, necessary for a modern society nowadays, and there are more destructive models broadcast from television screens and the Internet.

The tourism industry and culture, as observations show, form the following behavioral models: response in non-standard, extreme situations, psychological stability when interacting with different audiences, different in composition, quantity, model of “living in society” and expressing oneself from a creative point of view, as well as a model of expansion of consciousness through the formation of associative rows. At the moment, behavioral models in the field of tourism are being investigated from the point of view of a consumer of services, the importance of vocational guidance of young people through sports and health tourism and local history has long been proven, but the study of socialization issues through the above forms is promising.

The fundamental goal in all our studies is the education of a linguistic personality. Referring to the well-known saying “we are what we think”: cognitive content is formed by means of the Logos – words and meanings that are hidden behind it and sometimes replay everything else. When a person learns a language, he/she learns millions of bits of information. And the basis of the part is the lexical semantics, that is, words and their meanings. This is more than 2000 bytes of linguistic information per day, in addition, all this information is presented in unstable units [12].

In this case, the question arises of what and how to teach, i.e. on the development of a methodological approach, on the connection between input and output factors, their systematization and transformation into an educational form. We are talking about the creation of an algorithm (a system of sequential actions), leading to a highly effective linguoculturological process.

In the process of communication, the addressee implements “informational, influencing and hedonistic tasks; sightseeing, tourist rhetoric is a complex genre (may include fragments of various genres), is focused on an extremely efficient organization of information (related to scientific and popular sub-genres of scientific style, combines verbal and nonverbal information components [12], allowing you to build a methodology of formation of linguistic identity.

The process of interrelation of initial data, parameters of the linguistic personality and variable changes in the recipient’s worldview can be described using the following formulas.

The conditions for variable changes in the recipient’s worldview can be represented by the following formula:

$$\sum_{n=1}^7 (IN n) \infty \sum_{k=1}^k Pk(iL) \infty \sum_{L=1}^L (Vkmr L), \quad (2)$$

where *IN* is the incoming information flow; *P* are the parameters of the recipient’s world; *KMR* – the recipient’s worldview;

V – variable changes in *KMR*; ∞ – proportionality. Thus, the higher and more variable changes in the *KMR* we want to obtain, the higher the intensity of the input flows that affect the parameters of the *LI* is necessary.

The relationship between personality parameters and new connections in neural networks can be represented by the following formula:

$$\sum P \in CNS, \quad (3)$$

where *C* is the connection; *NS* – neural network, \in – affiliation. The more parameters of the *LI* at the input, the more new connections in the neural network of the *LI*.

The concepts of “linguistic identity” and “linguistic worldview” are not constant, but change under the influence of a number of factors and normally constantly expand, which makes this area promising for research [12]. The culture of a specialist’s speech is the ability to clearly express one’s thoughts, correctly use linguistic means in speech communication and is an indicator of socialization. The formation and transformation of meaning takes place on the basis of a linguistic personality and only after that it is transmitted outside. The dynamics of the development of society lies in the development of youth. And socialization is one of the most important development factors.

In order to obtain such a personality as a result, it is necessary to activate and initiate input information channels, improve neural networks [12].

4. Discussion

Understanding of language, context, meanings, which is what the excursion rhetoric says, is the basis for understanding the surrounding space and the basis for the formation of a linguistic personality. The task of forming a linguistic personality is not limited exclusively to professional competencies and the development of linguistic techniques, but also to the ability to transform and broadcast information, including influencing the recipients’ worldview.

A highly cultured *LI* is a system of knowledge, skills and manners, i.e. values, formed by harmonious upbringing and multiplicative education with developed information input and output streams. Now we are talking about multiplicative education as a modern trend that meets the needs of society and solves a number of pressing problems.

Within the framework of the Uralym project, a youth socialization project, this article serves as a tool for substantiating the importance of the tourism industry as a basic tool for youth socialization. Further research is aimed at detailing the toolkit in terms of the formation of a linguistic personality – a representative of youth through tourism, local history, art, traditions, culture of speech, the study of worldview of inhabitants of a polylingual region, toponymy.

One of the main conclusions of the work is that the greatest result in terms of socialization was revealed when compiling all the methods, but based on the use of the tourism sector. Two schoolchildren from classes, where the comparative methodological work was carried out, entered the 1st year of the *PF* BashSU. During the year of study, the second student was able to integrate into the intensive curriculum and practically “caught up” by the estimated parameters of the group. Immersion in the tourism and excursion sphere has become a stimulus for the development of a linguistic personality.

To achieve the maximum effect, an integrated approach was tested using elocution and psycholinguistic techniques. To form competencies, the following approach was used: compilation of

the maximum number of input information flows, which made it possible to improve and enhance the effectiveness of the presentation and processing of material by linguistic individuals. Quantitative indicators correspond to 70–75 % improvement in the quality of reproduced working material.

The development of an algorithm and methodological forms of multiplicative education requires innovative methods for training teaching staff, first of all, disclosing their personal professional characteristics and involvement in the creative educational process. The use of practice-oriented directions is a necessary factor for the modern training of specialists.

5. Conclusion

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Received date 22.02.2021

Accepted date 15.03.2021

Published date 31.03.2021

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How to cite: Akhmetshina, A., Biktimirova, D. (2021). *Student’s socialization: problems and mechanisms of implementation through the development of a linguistic identity*. *Technology Transfer: Innovative Solutions in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 4, 50–52. doi: <http://doi.org/10.21303/2613-5647.2021.001720>